

EELISA

European University

**EELISA INNOCORE EELISA MULTI LABS (SHARING FACILITIES
& EQUIPMENT)**

**Deliverable 4.5 - Definition of process for developing joint
infrastructures**

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This deliverable is the result of the work made in WP4 *EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)*.

The objective of the task was to define how common brand-new facilities can be implemented following a common preparation and eventually joint funding.

A bottom-up strategy for the development of joint research infrastructures has been discussed and agreed among the partners and the procedures and associated tools allowing its practical implementation have been defined.

Thanks to this procedure, we aim at creating more sustainable links between researchers and to foster the setup of joint facilities relying on the expertise of the researchers of different EELISA nodes and thus finally to obtain a higher degree of collaborative research between the EELISA partners.

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Responsibles for WP4

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for WP4
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Ecole Nationale Des Ponts Et Chaussees	ENPC	Mr. Emmanuel GIRARD, Deputy director of Research Department & Mr. Mustafa SEVIMLI Project Manager
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nuernberg	FAU	Mr. David SCHKADE, Strategic Projects Department
Istanbul Teknik Universitesi	ITÜ	Mrs Bihter Zeytuncu Gökoğlu, Professor
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Mr Pasqualantonio PINGUE, Head of Research & Innovation AREA and CCO at NEST Laboratory
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Universitatea Politehnica Din Bucuresti	UPB	Mr Catalin NEGRU, Senior Researcher
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Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the EELISA teams have been consulted for the production of this deliverable.

Quality check of this document was conducted by UPM (1st Quality Check) and Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa as quality assurance coordinator of EELISA InnoCORE (2nd Quality Check).

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

Research Infrastructures. The term “Research infrastructures” includes any piece of equipment that might be available to ‘customer’ whether they are in a laboratory (commercial device or developed/customed by researchers themselves), on a platform.

Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centres, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 44 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years, and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a collective strategic research area and research infrastructure map (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 11: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 Rationale and purposes

The work performed in WP4 has already allowed to:

i) create and publish a catalogue of the existing facilities (D4.1); <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-catalogue-of-research-facilities/>; <https://infrastructure.eelisa.eu/>

ii) define some basic rules of sharing and access (D4.2) and iii) develop the IT tools enabling the researchers get in contact and access the facilities (D4.3).

These actions enabled 1) to increase the visibility of the existing equipment and facilities but also of the research teams hosting them, and 2) to facilitate the interaction between researchers, two objectives that have been considered as a first step to initiate new collaborations between researchers and thus, in a longer term, also to enhancement students' and researchers' mobility.

As a further step to increase collaborations and integration of researchers belonging to different EELISA nodes, we explored the possibility of sharing expertise and funding to develop common research infrastructures. The outcome of the survey concerning research infrastructures funding sources (performed as D4.4) allowed to point out that not only the Alliance members are facing very different situations with regards to research infrastructure funding but also, and more relevantly, that the setup of research infrastructures is mostly a bottom-up process relying on proposals stemming directly from the active research groups. Furthermore, from the survey it was also emerging that the contribution to joint infrastructure has to be intended in terms more general than simple co-funding and the contributions of other partners such as scientific ones interested in a common development or use of a given facility are equally relevant, including a partnership for the success in national or European calls for specific funding.

On these bases, we thus proceeded to define:

i) the type of joint infrastructure that will be the target of our procedure, ii) the process allowing the proposal of joint research infrastructures following a bottom-up philosophy and iii) the associated tools enabling its practical implementation.

Overall, it is important to stress that with this bottom-up approach, we will not select a-priori specific area of interest in joint infrastructures that will be supported: the shared research infrastructure will come as a result of a joint call for partnership or by expression of interest by a network of users.

2.1 Definition of the target infrastructures in the framework of D4.5

While building the "catalogue of infrastructures/facilities" we let open the possibility of including all type of infrastructures, going from a single equipment developed (or used) in research/teaching laboratory to larger platforms (including service platforms). Indeed, the aim of the catalogue was to increase visibility of infrastructure/equipment-related activities in the EELISA partnership and to allow our researchers to get in contact and create new collaborations/projects.

The infrastructures that are the target of the process described in D4.5 are, on the other hand, essentially research-driven equipment/platforms, for which a widening of the users community among the EELISA partners represents a real added value either from the scientific point of view (the other partners bring the necessary expertise and competences to build and employ the facility) or from an impact point of view (the other partners can be additional users of the

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funded facilities). The acquisition of some of these infrastructures is expected to be only possible or requires a partnership (co)funding in specific and dedicated calls, at national or European level.

These calls are primarily those listed in the D4.4 Annex document named “Calls for research infrastructures”.

2.2 Definition of the process for developing joint research infrastructures

With the aim of coordinating the acquisition of novel infrastructures by each partner and in future also contribute to the setup of shared infrastructures (object of WP4 task 4.3 and 4.4), we want to define a process that ensures the coordination among partners in the acquisition of local infrastructures by each EELISA node and allow to share between all the partners sufficient information to setup new joint and/or shared infrastructures.

This process needs at a least sharing information concerning:

1. The existing infrastructures
2. The plans for novel infrastructures acquisition and of their funding scheme

For point 1) the existing online [catalogue of infrastructures](#) (which is fully open for consultation to all members of the Alliance) can be used. Of course, at least at the moment, the catalogue is far from being exhaustive, but this situation is expected to improve as soon as the visibility (and thus the number of facilities listed) increases.

For point 2), on the basis of the discussions between the WP4 members and of the outcomes of task 4.1 to task 4.3, we need to establish a fluid flow of information between i) the researchers of each EELISA node who, in a bottom-up approach, are actually those proposing the setup of novel facilities, and ii) the relevant community of researchers present at each of the other nodes that maybe interested in participating to the setup of the novel shared facilities.

To this end, we have decided any researcher of the EELISA Alliance should be enabled to post a request for developing a joint infrastructure through a specific form (that will be detailed in section 3 and that is given in annex) and to nominate a “referent person of infrastructures” for each EELISA partner. The role of the referent person will be the following: 1) keeping the catalogue of the shared infrastructures updated; and 2) transmitting the information related to what other partners plan to acquire to the interested researchers of its own EELISA node.

Indeed, the referent persons will be the recipient of the request form for joint infrastructure posted by the researchers and their role will be to share them within the researcher community of their respective nodes.

The “referent person of infrastructures” nominated for each node should thus be a person in contact with the research infrastructure community of each partner but he/she could also be more in general a member of the support teams (academic or administrative staff) helping the researchers of each node in their application to the various funding call. Of course, each EELISA partner, depending on its organization, is fully free to identify the best person for this purpose and to select the best way of spreading the information among its researchers.

The list of the current referent person of infrastructures is provided in Table 2

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Table 2: List of referent person of infrastructure for each EELISA node

Partner	Acronym	Referent person for infrastructure
Universidad Politecnica De Madrid	UPM	Ms Isabel SALGUEIRO Project Manager (until the end of EELISA InnoCORE)
Ecole Nationale Des Ponts Et Chaussees	ENPC	Mr.Mustafa SEVIMLI Project Manager
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nuernberg	FAU	Mr. David SCHKADE, Strategic Projects Department
Istanbul Teknik Universitesi	ITÜ	Mrs Bihter Zeytuncu Gökoğlu, Professor
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Mr Pasqualantonio PINGUE, Head of Research & Innovation AREA and CCO at NEST Laboratory
Scuola Superiore Di Studi Universitari E Di Perfezionamento S Anna	SSSA	Ms. Sara BARSANTI, Project Manager
Universitatea Politehnica Din Bucuresti	UPB	Mr Catalin NEGRU, Senior Researcher
Budapesti Muszaki Es Gazdasagtudomanyi Egyetem	BME	Mr. László LENGYEL, Director of Center for University-Industry Cooperation
Universite Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Ms. Ilaria CIOFINI, VP Research @ Chimie ParisTech PSL

Obviously, there is not a mandatory action, as already for the existing research infrastructure catalogue: each researcher/partner is free to share the information and acquisition plans or not.

3 Description of the form

Following discussions held in WP4, it turned out that to enable the setup of joint infrastructure the circulation of information among researchers is of primary importance. Different types of proposal were made ranging from publication and update of the joint acquisition plans through shared documents, or via publication on the website to more elaborate and interactive solutions analogous to the existing catalogue of infrastructures. From the discussions between the Alliance members, it turned that a good balance between efficiency and easiness in implementation can be represented by a simple form that the researchers can fill and that will be spread among the researcher's community by the referent persons.

This form (reported in Annex) contains the minimal information on the infrastructure project and needs and, more importantly, a direct contact (e-mail) that will allow the further direct interaction between the researchers of the different nodes. In such a way, the researchers will not need to systematically check for different openings and each node will keep track of the projects going on via the institutional contact.

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Indeed, once posted the form will be automatically distributed to the referent persons listed in Table 2 that will distribute it to their EELISA node community adding the following sentence: *If you are interested in joining this infrastructural project you should contact the “Scientific contact point” putting in cc the “Institutional contact point”.*

By doing so, there is also minimum exposure of email addresses on the web.

The online form (detailed in Annex 1) will appear on the EELISA website on the same page of the infrastructure catalogue. In such a way, the form will be clearly visible to the researchers of all institutions. During the time needed for the IT implementation of this online form, a temporary excel sheet shared on the EELISA SharePoint to update the infrastructures information will be used to collect and share the information.

4 Conclusions

With the procedure proposed, the development of joint research infrastructures following a bottom-up approach will be possible and accessible to the researchers of all EELISA institutions. The administrative burdens will be as low as possible for researchers and the spreading of information will benefit from the presence of local referent persons for infrastructure that will select channel to spread the information. It is expected that the setup of this procedure it will boost existing or new collaborations between our researchers and, at long term, enable an optimization of the research facility among the partners.

As further development, it would be interesting to create an “EELISA working group (consisting of the current members of WP4 of Innocore) that will consult WP9 on the subject of shared infrastructure. We also suggest having a small workshop explaining to the researchers and PHD students about this tool during the next EELISA event (student scientific competition, for example). In the long term, the catalogue of infrastructures could be further improved in the framework of EELISA 2.0, especially in WP4 from a technical point of view and in WP9 as a tool to continue supporting the creation of dialogue and synergies within the Alliance on common research areas and structures, to foster collaboration among PhD students and researchers, and providing young talents with the necessary means to excel in their future careers. These two suggestions come from on dialogue with the coleaders of WP9 within EELISA 2.0 dedicated for research.

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Annex 1 – Current form for the development of ‘joint infrastructures’

“Seek for support for joint infrastructures” form

This is a “seek for support for joint infrastructures” form allowing to automatically post a request to the list of referent persons of infrastructures for each EELISA partner. The distribution of the information collected via this form within each EELISA node is the full responsibility of the referent persons and each of them is free to choose the most adapted way. Two types of support are defined : i) co-funding ii) declaration of interest as user or as co-developers of a specific joint infrastructure from the researchers of other EELISA institutions.

Identify yourself

First Name

Last Name

Position

Select your host institution:

- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)
- Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME)
- Ecoles des Ponts ParisTech (ENPC)
- Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)
- Istanbul Technical University (ITU)
- Scuola Normale Superiore (SNS)
- Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA)
- Politehnica University of Bucharest (UPB)
- Université PSL (PSL)

Laboratory/Institute:

E-mail address:

(Please enter a valid e-mail address. It will be used for all further correspondence)

Select the type of support you are looking for:

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- Co-funding
- Declaration of interest as user or as co-developer of the joint infrastructure from the researchers of other EELISA institutions

Select the type of funding source you have/are applying to:

- Academic : European/National/regional/ call
- Local funds
- Industrial Support

Please specify the call and the deadline (provide a link to the call if available)

Description of the infrastructure

1. Provide a brief description of the infrastructure you are willing to setup

[max 5000 characters, excluding spaces]!

2. Provide a brief description of the support you are seeking from the EELISA partner

For co-funding include total cost and budget needed. [max 5000 characters, excluding spaces]!

Contact information :

Coordinates of the Scientific contact point (e-mail to be used for further correspondence):

Coordinates of the Institutional contact point :

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